

CHEMISTRY SCIENCES

СИНТЕЗ И ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ИОНООБМЕННЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ЭПОКСИАКРИЛАТОВ

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SYNTHESIS AND RESEARCH OF ION-EXCHANGE MATERIALS BASED ON EPOXYACRYLATES

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Аннотация

В статье исследованы возможности получения простой метод синтеза новых анионитов на основе двойных и тройных сополимеров глицидилметакрилата и полиаминов. Определены оптимальные условия синтеза и изучены физико-химические свойства ионно-связующего вещества. Состав и строение анионита определяли методом инфракрасной спектроскопии. Представленный анионит на основе ГМА - СТ-АКН и полиаминов является перспективным в процессе ионообмена и используется для выделения различных ионов металлов из водных растворов в области гидрометаллургии.

Abstract

The article investigates the possibilities of obtaining a simple method for the synthesis of new anionites based on double and triple copolymers of glycidyl methacrylate and polyamines. Optimal synthesis conditions were determined and the physicochemical properties of the ion-binder were studied. The composition and structure of anionite were determined by infrared spectroscopy. The presented anionite based on GMA - ST-ACN and polyamines is promising in the process of ion exchange and is used to isolate various metal ions from aqueous solutions in the field of hydrometallurgy.

Ключевые слова: Акрилонитрил, полиамины, глицидилметакрилат, стирол, сополимеризация, ионы металлов, сорбция.

Keywords: Acrylonitrile, polyamines, glycidyl methacrylate, styrene, copolymerization, metal ions, sorption.

Synthetic soluble and mesh ionites obtained on the basis of various monomers and copolymers are widely used in wastewater treatment, chromatography, hydrometallurgy, for the separation of metal ions, in the food and pharmaceutical industries, medicine and other industries [1]. With the development of science, much attention is paid to the problem of creating new ion-exchange materials with improved properties and structure based on reactive monomers and oligomers with active complex functional groups available to researchers. In this regard, intensive research is being conducted in the field of synthesis of complex (chelating) ionites and their application.

The requirements of modern society for science is the production of competitive products with high economic and environmental efficiency. Therefore, depending on the needs of science and economics, an urgent issue is the search and launch of simple methods for obtaining ion-exchange sorbents with high sorption capacity with improved physico-chemical properties, suitable for repeated use, cheap at the price of raw materials and products.

When using ion exchangers for special purposes, their ability to absorb substances with a relatively high molecular weight is taken into account. As a rule, ion exchangers are produced on the basis of styrene and

divinylbenzene copolymers [2]. The possibility of controlling the amount of divinyl compound in the initial mixture of monomers during copolymerization and, most importantly, the availability of the obtained copolymers for various polymeranalogical transformations opens up great opportunities. Ionites based on them have low kinetic properties and low availability of active groups for large ions. Macro-ion exchangers may be the most effective, but modern methods of synthesis of such sorbents have disadvantages. This is the complexity of obtaining ionites with high physicochemical parameters, the unavailability and toxicity of some initial monomers. Therefore, despite numerous studies in the field of synthesis of ion-exchange materials, the search for more accessible and acceptable ways to obtain new ionites of spatial structure with specified properties remains relevant [3].

In this regard, in the field of synthesis of sorbents with improved sorption and kinetic characteristics, highly permeable mesh polyelectrolytes, whose physicochemical properties have a high rate of absorption of valuable large-sized ions, are glycidyl ether (GMA) of methacrylic acid, the structural features of which cause the possibility of its radical homo-epoxy groups capable of participating in hardening reactions in the pres-

ence of acids and basic natural compounds are copolymerized by various vinyl monomers to produce reactive copolymers [4].

The introduction of additional functional groups into the sorbent structure leads to the formation of new adsorption centers, increasing the sorption capacity and the choice of sorbent. An urgent issue is their isolation from technological solutions by choosing the right method of modification, preserving the solid skeleton of the mineral and giving it new qualities and properties selectively related to radionucleotides and various related metals.

The aim of the work is to synthesize and study by physico-chemical methods the composition and structure of chelating anionites containing amine, phosphorus groups with good absorbent, highly permeable properties of new metal ions, their application in heavy metal hydrometallurgy [5].

Synthesis of a triple copolymer of glycidyl methacrylate (GMA) with styrene (ST) and acrylonitrile (ACN) by a radical method in a solution of dioxane GMA: ST: ACN = 60:20:20 mol. implemented in a % ratio. The copolymer was synthesized by radical polymerization at a temperature of 90°C in an ampoule with molybdenum glass and a dioxane solvent filled with inert argon gas.

Condensation of linear and cross-linked copolymers of GMA-ST-AKN with polyethylene polyamine, polyethylenimines (PEP, PEI) copolymer in an environment of organic solvents: polyamine (PEI, PEI) 1,0:1,0; 1,0:3,0; 1,0:6,0 carried out in the mass ratio. A

pre-weighed mass of amine (PEI, PEP) is placed in a triangular convex flask equipped with a mechanical mixer, a thermometer and a drip funnel, or a volume of a solution dissolved in a solvent is poured. After that, a copolymer solution (GMA-ST-ACN), previously dissolved in organic solvents dioxane or dimethylformamide, was gradually poured through a drip funnel. By intensive mixing with a mechanical stirrer, the mixture was heated at a temperature of 80-90 ° C until a thick mass was formed [6].

The most optimal mode of obtaining anionites based on GMA-ST-ACN-PEP is 10-hour heating at the mass ratio of the initial components (GMA-ST- ACN-PEP) 1:6 and 90 ° C, and for GMA-ST- ACN -PEI anionite, heating at 80 ° C in a ratio of 1:3. The static exchange capacity of anionites is 8.8 mg-eq/ g for GMA-ST- AKN-PEI in a solution of 0.1 n HCl with a yield of 79%.

And for GMA-ST- ACN-PEP, the static exchange capacity was 8.4 mg-eq / g in a solution of 0.1 n HCl, the yield of which was 80%.

IR spectra of polymer anionite samples are recorded on a Nicolet 5700 FT-IR spectrophotometer (Thermo Electron, USA) using potassium bromide in tablet form. To do this, sorbent samples were mixed with KBr salt (200 mg Kg and 1-2 mg of the test substance), crushed and pressed into tablets. After receiving the results of the IR spectrum, the spectra were determined using various techniques and the functional groups in them were characterized.

Fig.1. IR spectrum of GMA-ST- AKN -PEI anionite

Fig.2. IR spectrum of GMA-ST-ACN-PEP anionite

The IR spectra of GMA-ST-ACN-PEI anionites, as can be seen from Fig.1-2, have a great similarity with GMA-ST-ACN-PEI, which may be due to a similar chemical structure. Their spectra do not have frequencies characteristic of epoxy groups ($780,0-877,8$; $3000-3010\text{ cm}^{-1}$). On the contrary, new bands of deformation vibrations of N-H ($1556-1654\text{ cm}^{-1}$) bonds of amino groups and valence vibrations of C-N ($1062-1091\text{ cm}^{-1}$) appear [7], which indicates the chemical interaction of the copolymer GMA-ST-ACN with polyamines (PEI, PEP).

Conclusion, the issues of wastewater treatment are being solved, the environmental situation is improving. Also, due to the improved properties, highly permeable ionites can be used in the nuclear, oil industry, water treatment [8]. Thus, as a result of research work, it is possible to obtain copolymers of epoxyacrylates and anion exchangers based on polyamines with improved physico-chemical characteristics used for practical purposes in the field of hydrometallurgy.

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